

Percentage of Graduates in Italian Regions

Istat calculates the percentage of high school graduates in the Italian regions in the population between 25 and 64 years. In 2019, Puglia ranks last for graduates.

Istat calculates the percentage of high school graduates in the Italian regions in the population between 25 and 64 years. The data refer to the Istat-BES database in 2019. In first place in the ranking is Umbria with a value of 71.3%, followed by Lazio with a value of 70.3% and Friuli - Venezia Giulia with a value of 70.1%. In the middle of the table there are Tuscany with a value of 64.8%, followed by Veneto with a value of 64.7% and Lombardy with a value of 64.5%. Campania closes the ranking with a value of 51.8%, Sicily with a value of 51.8% and Puglia with a value of 51.3%.

Ranking of the regions by variation in the number of graduates as a percentage of the resident population between 2004 and 2019. Friuli-Venezia Giulia ranks first for overall variation in the number of graduates as a percentage of the resident population between 2004 and 2019. a value of 18.5, followed by Trentino Alto-Adige with an amount of 18.2 and by Veneto with an amount of 17.5. In the middle of the table there are Sardinia with a value of 14.9 units, Umbria with a value of 14.3 units and Abruzzo with a value of 14 units. Sicily closes the ranking with a value of 10.7 units, followed by Campania with a value of 10.3 units and Calabria with a value of 8.1 units.

The change in the number of graduates in Northern Italy. The percentage of the number of graduates in Northern Italy as a percentage of the population between 25 and 64 years has grown from a value of 63.2% to a value of 65.7% or a variation equal to an amount of 2.5 units equivalent to an amount of 4.00%. Specifically, the percentage of graduates in 2015 was equal to a value of 63.2% in 2015 and subsequently increased to a value of 63.5% or equal to a variation of 0.30 units equal to an amount of 0.47%. In the transition between 2016 and 2017, the value of the percentage of graduates in Northern Italy as a percentage of the resident population increased from a value of 63.5% to a value of 64.5% or equal to a variation of 1 units equal to an amount of 1.57%. Between 2017 and 2018, the percentage of graduates increased from a value of 64.5% to a value of 65.5% or equal to a variation of 1 unit equal to a value of 1.55%. Between 2018 and 2019 the value of the percentage of graduates in Northern Italy grew from an amount of 65.5% to a value of 65.7% or equal to a value of 0.2 units equal to an amount of 0.3%.

Center. In the transition between 2015 and 2019 the value of the percentage of graduates increased from a value of 66.6% to a value of 68.1% or equal to a growth of 1.5 units equal to a value of 2.3%. In 2015 the value of the number of graduates in the Center was equal to 66.6% and subsequently, in 2016, this value increased to a value of 66.70% or a change equal to an amount of 0.10 units equal to a value of 0.15%. In the transition between 2016 and 2017, the percentage value of the number of graduates in the Center increased from an amount equal to 66.70% up to a value equal to 67.40% or equal to a value of 0.7 units equal to at a value of 1.049%. In the transition between 2017 and 2018, the value of the percentage of graduates in Central Italy increased from an amount of 67.4% to a value of 67.70% or equal to a variation of 0.30 units equal to an amount of 0.45%. In the transition between 2018 and 2019 the value of the percentage of graduates in Central Italy increased from an amount

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equal to 67.70% up to a value equal to 68.10% or equal to a value of 0.4 units equal to an amount of 0.60%.

Southern Italy. The percentage of high school graduates in Southern Italy increased from an amount equal to 51.6% to a value of 54.00% or equal to a value of 2.4 units equal to a variation of 4.7%. In the transition between 2015 and 2016 the value of the percentage of graduates increased from an amount equal to 51.6% up to a value of 51.80% or equal to a value of 0.20 units equal to an amount of 0.39%. In the transition between 2016 and 2017, the percentage of high school graduates in Southern Italy increased from an amount equal to 51.80% to an amount of 52.5% or equal to a variation of 0.7 units equal to an amount of 1.35%. In the transition between 2017 and 2018 the value of the percentage of graduates in Southern Italy increased from an amount equal to 52.5 units up to a value equal to 54.00 units or equal to an amount of 0.7 units equal to a value of 1.3%.

Conclusions. In summary, it should be considered that the percentage of graduates in the Italian regions in the population between 25 and 64 years of age has certainly grown in the period between 2004 and 2019 in all regions and also in macro-regions. However, there are some regions that still show very low values of the percentage of graduates out of the total resident population, such as Puglia where only one in two people aged 25-64 has a diploma. The question of education policies is therefore still open and requires interventions to strengthen educational institutions and connections between the school system and the university system, as well as greater leadership of the educational institution in local communities.

Declarations

Acknowledgment. I want to thank the colleagues of the Lum Enterprise S.r.l. and prof. Alberto Costantiello and Lucio Laureti of LUM University Giuseppe Degennaro.

Data Availability Statement. The data presented in this study are available on request from the corresponding author.

Funding. The author received no financial support for the research, authorship, and/or publication of this article.

Declaration of Competing Interest. The author declares that there is no conflict of interests regarding the publication of this manuscript. In addition, the ethical issues, including plagiarism, informed consent, misconduct, data fabrication and/or falsification, double publication and/or submission, and redundancies have been completely observed by the authors.

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